

EVALUATION OF ANTIBACTERIAL - MICROBIAL PERFORMANCE OF BETA PHASE TITANIUM COPPER ALLOY FOR INTRAUTERINE GYNAECOLOGICAL APPLICATION

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14785074>

Published Date: 01-February-2025

Abstract: The research study on the anti-bacterial property of beta phase TiCu alloy was handled by antibacterial test on Escherichia Coli(E,C) and Staphylococcus Aureus(S.A) colonies on the specimens. Research studies indicated that the Ti 17%Cu alloy specimen exhibited excellent antibacterial property, providing a great potential in clinical application for gynaecological implants. The research of antimicrobial/antibiofilm activities of the beta phase contraceptive Titanium Copper alloy (TiCu) against these bacterial species showed an excellent antibacterial effect in vitro, thus inhibiting both Escherichia coli and Staphylococcus Aureus. This research innovated the design and production of Beta(β) phase TiCu alloy specimens in the categories of ; Ti0.5%Cu, Ti1.0%Cu, Ti2.0%Cu, Ti5.0%Cu, Ti10.0%Cu, Ti15.0%Cu and Ti17.0% Cu, using Copper element as the experimental control reference biomaterial. The TiCu alloy specimens were produced by powder metallurgy technique in an inert environment. Experimental investigations and Minitab Software Design analyses on these specimens for combined antibacterial response in direct improvement of mechanical compatibility (tensile strength, hardness value, fracture toughness), biocompatibility–cell viability (cytocompatibility), corrosion resistance by Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS), contraceptive response integrity(CRI) and the effect of surface treatment were all carried out in order to establish the suitability of Ti17%Cu alloy as a possible replacement to the existing prototype biomaterial(Cu-T380(IUD)).

Keywords: biomaterials, contraceptive, titanium copper alloy, gynaecological, beta phase, specimens, endometrium, Cu T380IUD, intra uterine.

1. INTRODUCTION

Most metals (Cu ,Ag ,Zn etc) have been reported as being antibacterial agents in metallic matrix. Therefore, elements alloyed with these trace elements are used to develop antibacterial biomaterial metals for orthopaedic, gynaecological and dental implants. Copper element is a prominent material alloyed with other elements in order to establish antibacterial property. Recently, most metals having eutectic alloy composition are used as biomaterial with antibacterial response (Erin Zhang, 2013)

Titanium alloy exhibited excellent antibacterial property and corrosion resistance, providing a great potential in clinical application for gynaecological implants. Also 420-CuSS presented excellent antibacterial performance against colonies of bacteria, including, Escherichia Coli (E.coli) and Staphylococcus Aureus (S. Aureus), with approximately 99.4% of antibacterial rate. Further studies suggested that 316L SS coated with a TiCu layer (316L/TiCu) showed an effective reduction of 99.9% of Escherichia coli within 12 h 127min (Chen, 2004). In addition, developed alloy containing antibacterial Titanium alloy (Ti5Cu), possess strong antibacterial activity against both Escherichia Coli (E.C) and Staphylococcus Aureus(S.A). The antimicrobial/antibiofilm activities of TiCu alloy(alpha) against the orally specific bacterial species Streptococcus Mutans and Porphyromonas Gingivalis showed an excellent antibacterial effect both in vitro and in vivo, thus inhibiting Escherichia coli. Ti5%Cu have Strong antibacterial activity against both Escherichia coli and Staphylococcus Aureus (Hong, 2005).

Biomaterial research reports established that human tissue is mainly organised of self-assembled polymers (proteins) and ceramics (bone materials), having metal constituents as trace elements (Qizh and George, 2015). These trace metal elements are Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Ag^{2+} e.t.c, which create contraceptive response resulting in immotility of the spermatozoa and inability of ova fertilization by the principle of actions of inhibition of both glycolytic oxygen and glucose uptake by the spermatozoa. The application of metals and alloys for biomedical contraceptive within the endometrium host environment is a research innovation, not yet explored fully. Williams(2013), a biomedical expert, reported that heavy metal ions possess spermicidal properties, and anchored this research finding on the effects of Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Co . Titanium has a phase transformation from alpha to beta phase at temperatures above 883°C . Below 882.5°C , Titanium exists as alpha-phase (α) material and the crystal structure is hexagonal close packed(Hcp), but above 883°C it changes to body centered cubic system(bcc) in beta(β) phase, because it possesses high passivity and regenerative properties i.e ability to repair itself and form protective covering, with dense oxide film(Coating, 2003). It is usually considered for biomaterial, and the low young modulus is very close to that of the bone (williams, 2013), which disallows the stress shielding effect associated with biomaterials of high modulus of elasticity, common to alpha (α) and alpha+beta ($\alpha + \beta$) phases. Titanium alloys are differentiated into three metallurgical groups, which are; alpha (α), Beta (β) and alpha+beta. Research has shown that copper phase stabilizes Titanium alloys, and these are qualitatively used in gynaecological biomaterial application, with very low modulus of Elasticity (which is below the α and $\alpha + \beta$ phase), and very close to human femoral bone modulus of elasticity of between 38 – 40GPA(Sammons, 2003). Titanium and its alloys in beta phase domain exhibit microstructure effects of Osseointegration, osteoconduction and osteoinduction properties of biomaterials. The Osteoinduction is an attribute of Titanium which guarantees bone healing process with formation of prosteoblasts, and the reduction of cracks and fractures initiated by corrosion process(Sutter and Bonni, 2005).

Figure 1: Insertion of IUD T380 in the Endometrium Ref; Kalpana Gupta (2009)

EXISTING PROBLEMS IN INTRAUTERINE CONTRACEPTIVE BIOMATERIAL

The problems of existing Intrauterine implants(CuT380) are basically expulsion, fragmentation, corrosion and infection phenomena. Figure 1 depicts the insertion of CuT380 in the endometrium, The occurrence of biodegradation and loss of material integrity are due to corrosion and wear thereby influencing the mechanical properties of the biomaterial, and usually lead to mechanical failure(Gilbert, 1993).

MATERIAL DESIGN OF CYLINDRICAL SPECIMENS BY PHASE DIAGRAM

Figure 2: Phase Diagram of Ti-Cu Alloy (courtesy, Good fellow Inc, USA)

In the material design, the production of Ti_xCu alloy specimens ($x=0.5\%, 1.0\%, 2.0\%, 5.0\%, 10.0\%, 15.0\%$ and 17.0%) is by powder metallurgy in an inert environment at eutectic maximum solubility of 17.0% copper in beta Titanium phase at $1005^\circ C$ and compaction pressure of $500MPa$, as depicted above, in the phase diagram of Titanium Copper alloy. The copper element (control reference material) powder is also processed in the inert environment at the temperature of $1005^\circ C$ (Udeh,2021).

PREPARATION OF SPECIMENS BY POWDER METALLURGY

The specimens were prepared by Powder metallurgy approach by;

- i. Copper: commercial pure copper powder named (cp-Cu) were used for the alloying, and also as specimen for the control reference experimental biomaterial.
- ii. Titanium-copper alloy (TiCu) specimen preparations, with prepared Titanium powder and Copper powder (99.5% pure) of different percentage weight compositions were as follows;

(99.5% Ti 0.5%Cu), (99% Ti 1.0%Cu), (98.0% Ti 2.0%Cu), (95.0% Ti 5.0%Cu)

(90.0% Ti 10.0%Cu), (85.0%Ti 15%Cu), (83% Ti 17%Cu).

The Titanium powder and copper powder were each weighed out differently, and ball milled differently for 4-7 hrs, and then were pressure compacted upto $500MPa$, to develop the specimens (TiCu Alloy), being 30mm in diameter, and under vacuum conditions of $983^\circ c - 1005^\circ c$ for 135-190 mins, and allowed to cool in furnace to room temperature of $30^\circ C$. The specimens of diameter 30mm and a thickness of 2.5cm were sliced-off from the TiCu specimens for the various tests (Udeh,2021).

Fig 3: Developed beta phase Titanium copper specimens and copper specimen

EXPERIMENTAL TESTS (DESIGN APPROACH)

The experimental tests conducted, within this biomaterial research work are as follows;

- (1) Electrochemical Corrosion resistance test (EIS)
- (2) Biocompatibility (cell viability / cell proliferation) test
- (3) Mechanical compatibility test (Tensile, Hardness, Fracture Toughness tests)
- (4) Antiseptic /Microbial test
- (5) Invitro Contraceptive response test
- (6) Microstructure and XRD Examination

Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy Test for Corrosion (EIS)

The electrochemical impedance spectroscopy experiments were conducted with the use of two fluids (Simulated Body Fluids) which are simulated to be identical to human fluids, controlled at 7.1 PH value, using Hanks solution and Ringers solution, This test is carried out at approximately 37⁰c ,with beakers containing the specimens. The open circuit potential (ocp) was measured for 1 hour(3600secs) of immersion of the specimens. The electrochemical impedance spectroscopy test for the specimens were conducted at a room temperature condition of 37⁰c, with scan from - 190mv v_{s,ocp}(open circuit potential) to + 1250 mv v_{s,ocp} at a scan rate of 0 .5mv/s . Impedance measurements were performed at +10mv amplitude upto 1hr, recording the electrochemical impedance spectroscopy spectra at approximately every 60secs for the measurement tests .

The corrosion rate is,

$$V = \frac{MI}{nF} \tag{3.4}$$

Where,

- M = molar mass of Titanium copper or Copper element
- I = Average corrosion rate
- F= Faradays Corrosion density
- n = Valency of element

Table 1: Hanks Solution

Substance	Composition (g L ⁻¹)
NaCl	8.0
KCl	0.4
NaHCO ₃	0.35
NaH ₂ PO ₄ .H ₂ O	0.25
Na ₂ HPO ₄ .2H ₂ O	0.06
CaCl ₂ .2H ₂ O	0.19
MgCl ₂	0.19
MgSO ₄ .7H ₂ O	0.06
Glucose	1.0
PH	6.9

Ref; (Aragon P.J,2009)

Table 2: Ringers solution

NaCl	8.69
KCl	0.30
CaCl ₂	0.48
PH	6.4

(Ref; Aragon P.J, 2009)

The biocompatibility tests of the specimens were investigated by the process of Cellular attachment (adhesion) and Mitochondrial activity (MTT) test of human osteoblast-derived cells compared to the bare substrate. The samples placed in 8 cultured plates and cells each, were plated and left to adhere for 3.5hrs, and after this duration, 500 microlitres of culture medium were added.

2. MECHANICAL COMPATIBILITY TEST

Microhardness test:

Microhardness test was handled by first polishing the specimens, and point of indentation mark occurrence on their surfaces recorded by the indentation machine. The value of the Brinell Hardness test is read off from the indentation machine, and recorded for each specimen of cylindrical dimension of 30mm and thickness of 25mm.

The Tensile test

The tensile and percentage elongation tests on the specimens were handled with the universal testing machine. The machine has a loading frame, and a controller plotter, with progressive strain rates of 0.01/sec, 0.015/sec, 0.020/sec, 0.025, 0.030/sec. The loads versus strains on each specimen were recorded.

Fracture Toughness Test:

Fracture toughness test on the specimens progresses with surface polishing to remove any indentation, and then an initial crack or v-groove notch is made on the surface of the specimen. The gradual loading on the machine commenced, and the load at which the test piece fails to resist crack propagation is recorded for each specimen.

Antiseptic Microbial Test

The antiseptic microbial tests on these samples, using colonies of staphylococcus Aureus and Escherichia Coli in plated and incubated media at 6-8 hours of incubation with the antibacterial rate, R, is calculated from the equation;

$$R = (N_{control} - N_{sample}) / N_{control} \% \quad (3.5)$$

Where,

$N_{control}$ = average number of bacteria on the control dish

N_{sample} = average number of bacteria on the sample dish

R > 99% denotes that sample has strong antibacterial property

R > 90% denotes that sample has simple antibacterial property

The invitro contraceptive (spermicidal) test is conducted by using the estimation of motility of the spermatozoa collected and their metabolism.

3. PREPARATION OF SPERMATOZOA

The Semen were collected from the laboratory. The semen is maintained at 37°C for 15 to 30 minutes. The spermatozoa were mixed by adopting gentle agitation. The spermatozoa is prepared by washing the spermatozoa free of seminal plasma and diluted with 5 volumes of free calcium Kreber Ringer phosphate (KRP) buffer (0.12m NaCl, 0.005m KCl, 0.0124m Mg SO₄, 0.016 m Sodium Phosphate, PH 7.4 at 37°C, and then centrifuged at 740 xg ($r_{av}=17cm$) for period of ten(10) minutes at 20°C. The aliquots are then removed and the spermatozoal suspension collected for use, with each specimen placed into each container.

Estimation Test of Motility

The use of flasks containing $1.01 \pm 0.1 \times 10^8$ spermatozoa, using the 300 Sq mm of the specimens to be tested and 3Mm glucose in KRP buffer were incubated for 3hrs with constant shaking at 37°C in a water bath, with Spermatozoa added at intervals of 30, 60, 120 and 180 minutes.

Evaluation Test of Metabolism

A special container having small flasks, and in which manometer was immersed in a thermostatically controlled bath assisted in measuring the oxygen consumption of the spermatozoa. Approximately, $1.01 \pm 0.1 \times 10^8$ spermatozoa were added to each flask, which contained 3Mm glucose ($0.5 \times 10^{-6} gm$ of glucose), and the 300 Sqmm of the specimens under test.

OBSERVATIONS;

Direct electronic microscopic observations were used for the evaluations.

4. RESULTS AND DATA ANALYSIS

In the development of Ti x%Cu (x= 0.5,1.0,2.0,.5.0,10.0,15.0 and 17.0 %) alloy specimens and copper element as reference control experiment, there is a research trend employing engineering Minitab design methodology for investigation, of designed experimental test on parameters such as biocompatibility status ,mechanical strength, corrosion resistance rate and antibacterial properties in order to establish the suitability of these specimens to function effectively as contraceptive biomaterial within the endometrium (Ullman and Hammerstein,1993).

MECHANICAL TESTS

TENSILE STRESS TEST AND PERCENTAGE ELONGATION RESULTS

The Tables below show the results

PLOTS OF TENSILE STRESS

Plots of Tensile stress versus strain for the various specimens are shown below;

- (1) Ti 0.5%Cu, (2)Ti 1.0%Cu, (3)Ti 2.0% Cu, (4)Ti 5.0%Cu,
- (5) Ti 10.0%Cu, (6)Ti 15.0%Cu, (7)Ti 17%Cu and (8) 100%Cu

Fig 4: Tensile test(Ti0.5%Cu)

Fig 5: Tensile test(1.0%Cu)

Fig 6: Tensile test (Ti2.0%Cu)

Fig 7: Tensile test (Ti5.0%Cu)

Fig 8: Tensile test (Ti10.0%Cu)

Fig 9: Tensile test(Ti 15.0%Cu)

Fig 10: Tensile test(Ti 17.0%Cu)

Fig 11: Tensile test(100%Cu)

Fig 12: Ultimate tensile Strength

Fig 13: Percentage Elongation

Fig 14: 0.25% Yield Stress

Fig 15: Brinell Hardness Value (BHV)

Fig 16: Fracture Toughness

4.3 CORROSION TEST RESULTS.

The corrosion potential of the specimens showed that Ti 17%Cu have value of -0.304 While copper indicated a corrosion potential of -0.243. .

HANKS SOLUTION SIMULATED BODY FLUID (SBF)

+Fig 17: Corrosion Potential

CORROSION RATE (HANKS)

Fig 18: Corrosion Rate (Hanks)

PLOT OF CORROSION RATE (RINGERS)

Fig 19: Corrosion Rate (Ringers)

BIOCOMPATIBILITY TEST RESULT

The biocompatibility – cell viability test showed that Ti 17%Cu has 155% viability while copper has 54% cell viability status. The Copper ion release is 0.029mg/Litre for Ti 17%Cu , while copper has ion release of 0.038mg/litre

CELL CYTOTOXICITY. COPPER ION RELEASE TEST

Fig 20: Copper ion Release (Cytotoxicity)

ANTIMICROBIAL - ANTISPETIC TEST RESULTS

The antiseptic microbial test on the specimens, in the cultured environment of each of Staphylococcus Aureus (S.A) and Escherisha Coli(E.C) colonies, indicated progressive antibacterial action. with increase in the percentage composition of copper. .

Fig 21: Staphylococcus Aureus (S.A)

Fig 22: Escherisha Coli (E.C)

INVITRO CONTRACEPTIVE RESPONSE TEST RESULTS

On the Contraceptive response test, the research initiated invitro simulative approach of percentage Motility rate and Glycolytic Metabolism assessment.

PERCENTAGE MOTILITY RATE

Fig 23: Invitro Contraceptive (Percentage Motility Rate)

Fig 24: Glycolytic Oxygen Uptake (invitro Contraceptive)

TABLE 3: Experimental Results for Minitab Software Design Analysis.

RESULTS FOR MINITAB ANALYSIS

SAMPLES	Ult	YIELD	FRA.	BHV	COIR	Ecorr	VIA	MOT	GLY	
TI	CU	MPA	MPA	MPA $M^{0.5}$	VALUE	Mg/cm2yr	-	%	%	%
99.5	0.5	600	550	50	250	1.22	-0.317	166	8	4.1
99.0	1.0	700	600	55	300	1.25	-0.315	165	5	4.32
98.0	2.0	780	688	60	330	1.30	-0.313	164	4	4.44
95.0	5.0	800	700	62	340	1.34	-0.310	160	3	4.5
90.0	10.0	810	720	65	350	1.36	-0.308	158	2	4.7
85.0	15.0	850	760	68	400	1.38	-0.305	156	1	5.4
83.0	17.0	900	790	72	450	1.40	-0.304	155	0.2	8.2
0.0	100.0	540	460	38	320	6.8	-0.242	54	0.1	9.5

8 (EIGHT) SAMPLES(Ti-TITANIUM %, Cu, = COPPER%)

Note: VALUED PARAMETERS

ULT -ULTIMATE TENSILE STRENGTH, YIELD- 0.25% YIELD STRENGTH, FRA - FRACTURE TOUGHNESS, BHV-BRINNEL HARDNESS VALUE, COIR- COPPER ION RELEASE RATE, Ecorr – CORROSION POTENTIAL,VIA-BIOCOMPATIBILITY VIABILITY PERCENT,MOT- SPERMATOOZA MOTILITY RATE, GLYM- GLYCOLYTIC METABOLISM.

TABLE 4: Modulus of Elasticity, E , of Specimen

SPECIMEN	VALUE OF E (GPa)
Ti 0.5% Cu	36
Ti 1.0% Cu	37
Ti 2.0% Cu	41
Ti 5.0% Cu	42
Ti 10.0% Cu	44
Ti 15.0% Cu	46
Ti 17.0% Cu	48
Copper(Cu)	30

Where, E= . YIELD STRESS/STRAINXFACTOR OF SAFETY (n) , n=1.10 (biomaterial)

Regression Model Equations and Statistical Deterministic Validation.

(1) Response Surface Regression: ULTIMATE STRESS versus Ti, Cu

Model Summary

S	R-sq	R-sq(adj)	R-sq(pred)
61.7267	85.93%	75.38%	*

Regression Equation;

$$ULT = 1051 + 13.2 Ti - 5.1 Cu - 0.1689Ti^2$$

(2)Response Surface Regression: YIELD STRESS versus Ti, Cu

Model Summary

S	R-sq	R-sq(adj)	R-sq(pred)
21.0212	94.87%	91.03%	*

Regression Equation ;

$$YIELD = -1559 + 31.9 Ti + 21.6 Cu - 0.1126 Ti^2$$

(3)Response Surface Regression: FRACTURE TOUGHNESS. versus Ti, Cu

Model Summary

S	R-sq	R-sq(adj)	R-sq(pred)
3.22114	95.02%	91.29%	*

Regression Equation;

$$FRA. = 24 + 1.73 Ti + 0.14 Cu - 0.01433 Ti^2$$

International Journal of Novel Research in Engineering and Science

 Vol. 11, Issue 2, pp: (44-58), Month: September 2024 - February 2025, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

(4)Response Surface Regression: BRINNEL HARDNESS VALUE, BHV versus Ti, Cu

Model Summary

S	R-sq	R-sq(adj)	R-sq(pred)
29.1618	86.89%	77.06%	*

Regression Equation;

$$\text{BHV} = 1976 - 6.5 \text{ Ti} - 16.6 \text{ Cu} - 0.1049 \text{ Ti}^2$$

(5)Response Surface Regression: COPPER ION RELEASE RATE versus Ti, Cu

Model Summary

S	R-sq	R-sq(adj)	R-sq(pred)
0.0017480	92.72%	87.27%	*

Regression Equation ;

$$\text{COIR} = 0.168 - 0.00114 \text{ Ti} - 0.00131 \text{ Cu} - 0.000003 \text{ Ti}^2$$

(6)Response Surface Regression: Ecorrosion Potential, versus Ti, Cu

Model Summary

S	R-sq	R-sq(adj)	R-sq(pred)
0.0043111	97.24%	95.16%	*

Regression Equation ;

$$\text{Ecorr} = 0.020 - 0.00556 \text{ TI} - 0.00263 \text{ CU} + 0.000027 \text{ TI}^2$$

(7)Response Surface Regression: Viability-Biocompatibility, versus TI, CU

Model Summary

S	R-sq	R-sq(adj)	R-sq(pred)
9.95772	94.95%	91.17%	*

Regression Equation;

$$\text{VIA} = -581 + 11.5 \text{ Ti} + 6.3 \text{ Cu} - 0.04769 \text{ Ti}^2$$

(8)Response Surface Regression: Motility Rate, versus Ti, Cu

Model Summary

S	R-sq	R-sq(adj)	R-sq(pred)
1.36955	85.34%	74.35%	*

Regression Equation ;

$$\text{MOT} = -84 + 0.53 \text{ Ti} + 0.84 \text{ Cu} + 0.00369 \text{ Ti}^2$$

(9)Response Surface Regression: Glycolytic metabolism Rate; GLYM versus Ti, Cu

Model Summary

S	R-sq	R-sq(adj)	R-sq(pred)
1.02616	85.60%	74.80%	*

Regression Equation;

$$\text{GLY} = 54 - 0.36 \text{ Ti} - 0.45 \text{ Cu} - 0.001428 \text{ Ti}^2$$

XRD AND SEM EXAMINATIONS

Fig 25: XRD PATTERN OF Ti 17% Cu AND COPPER FLEMENT

Fig 26: SEM MICROSTRUCTURE EXAMINATION

5. DISCUSSION

DEVELOPMENT OF SAMPLES (TiCu) BY POWDER METALLURGY

The development and analysis of the beta phase TiCu alloy (Bcc) specimens is innovated, using the highlighted characterized parameters which influenced the acceptability of the researched alloy, Titanium Copper alloy (Paul and Ronald, 1988). Titanium as an element is allotropic, existing in more than one crystalline form, which at room temperature is Hexagonal close packed (HCP) and of Alpha phase (Amir et al, 2015), but when alloyed with a Beta phase stabilizer, copper, at temperature of 928°C- 1005°C to form Titanium Copper alloy, there is a metallurgical phase transformation to Beta phase with Body centered cubic structure (Bcc) (Udeh, 2021) . .

MICROSTRUCTURE EXAMINATIONS AND MECHANICAL STRENGTH

The XRD and SEM microstructure analyses indicated the formation of Ti₂Cu intermetallic beta phase, with Bcc structure for all the beta phase Titanium copper alloy specimens (Qizh and George, 2015). This microstructural stability affected positively the mechanical strength. The microstructure of the Titanium Copper alloy, as shown in figure 26, indicates that the Copper powder is uniformly distributed within the Titanium matrix, and is an index for good mechanical strength (Congelo and Heiser, 1974). The Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) showed the presence of intermetallic Titanium copper, Ti₂Cu, which provided the interface for mechanical strength and good biocompatibility properties (Sykaras, 2000).

CORROSION RESISTANCE AND SURFACE FILM REGENERATION

Kobyashi et al (1988) and Fontana (1986) in similar research concluded that Titanium alloys when tested in both simulated body fluids (SBF) of Hanks solution and Ringers solution have very low corrosion rate. Sutter T. and Boni H. (2005) maintained that corrosion resistance of biomaterials, as in Ti17%Cu alloy, is best investigated using Electron Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS), Gonzalez and Mirza (2004) collaborated the research result on these TiCu alloys and confirmed that the low corrosion rate is due to the regenerative oxide film layer which forms protective film and prevents biological attacks by the plasma contents of Oxygen in human system. .

BIOCOMPATIBILITY

Chen (2018) research on biomaterial applications confirmed that TiCu alloys, as in the Ti17%Cu alloy, have very tolerable copper ion release which gives acceptable cell compatibility and viability to these biomaterials. The biocompatibility of the TiCu alloy, being evaluated by the principles of adhesion viability / proliferation assays, showed that it agreed with the research of Zielske et al 1974 which recorded high cell affinity of beta phase Titanium alloys, as in Ti17Cu%, within the interacting biological human tissues. .

ANTIBACTERIAL AND ANTISEPTIC PROPERTY

Ali (2004) proved that Ti alloys, as shown in the case of results of Ti17%Cu alloy, exhibited excellent antibacterial microbial quality performance against Escherichia Coli (E.Coli) and Staphylococcus Aureus (S.A), with an approximate 99.9% antibacterial rate. The normal vaginal system is reported to host urogenital bacteria and cause subsequent infections. The vaginal flora is disrupted by the presence of antibacterial biomaterial which has microbial and antiseptic properties (Kalpana, 2009). The Ti17% Cu response to the most common genital infections in the endometrium of staphylococcus aureus (S.A) and Escherichia coli (E.C) showed inhibition of the colony formation of these microbes, thereby providing good antiseptic qualities. .

INVITRO CONTRACEPTIVE RESPONSE

Ahti kosonen (1978) results agreed with Ti17%Cu alloy and proved that the copper ion release created immotile environment within the endometrium, that inhibited the fertilization of the ovum by the immotile spermatozoa. Zipper (1969) analysis, as in Ti17%Cu alloy, showed the effect of copper ion release which inhibited spermatozoan movement in the endometrium that creates infertility and contraceptive action.

VALIDATION OF RESULTS.

The Minitab software analyses confirmed the statistical Deterministic correlation of the variables (R²) for the parametric experimental analyses as $0.85 < R^2 < 0.95$. This regression relationship further confirms the high acceptability of the

research results in conformity with the research works of Jin et al (2015) and Erlin et al(2013) on characterization of Titanium based binary alloys.

6. CONCLUSION

Many researchers have worked on monoelements, copper(cu) and silver(Ag) materials to function as contraceptive device, but there is no record of research on the application of binary alloy, specifically beta(β) –phase(Bcc) Titanium copper(TiCu) alloy for gynaecological contraceptive application. Summarily, alloying of the elements (Ti and Cu) in an inert condition ,within the temperature of 928⁰C -1005⁰C achieved a eutectic (BCC) beta phase. Ti17%Cu alloy, which affects the microstructure and strengthening of mechanical properties of the contraceptive biomaterial (Ti17%Cu), .

CONTRIBUTION TO KNOWLEDGE

This experimental research has provided a knowledge interface in the development of a beta (β) phase biomaterial alloy(Ti17%Cu)with Bcc microstructure, that are anchored on software designed parametric model equations, thus proferring an improved alternative solution to intractable intrauterine contraceptive challenges of the existing monoelement, copper IUDT380 biomaterial.

Recommendations For Future Research work

- (1) Future research will be directed towards employing additional invivo tests on Ti17%Cu ,in animal and human systems, in order to augment the existing in vitro research analysis of Ti17%Cu alloy, with further pursuance of confirmatory approval of NAFDAC for patent certification of this research project.
- (2) Also, ageing heat treatment process that could optimize the mechanical strength, biocompatibility, Corrosion resistance and antiseptic microbial responses of the Ti17% Cu alloy is recommended.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors wish to acknowledge the contributions and support of the World Bank African Centre of Excellence for sustainable Power and Energy Development, University of Nigeria Nsukka.

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International Journal of Novel Research in Engineering and Science

 Vol. 11, Issue 2, pp: (44-58), Month: September 2024 - February 2025, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

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